

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Milestone MS8

Report providing the list of indicators of food and water security

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MILESTONE REPORT

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1. Means of verification

As stated in the Description of the Action, the means to verify that this milestone has been achieved are the following: “The document available on Zenodo in open access”.

2. About the work done to achieve this milestone

2.1 Food Security

Beyond food production, food security is affected by many social, political, and logistical factors. For instance, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) assesses food security on dimensions of availability, access, stability, and utilisation (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS>). Similarly, the Global Food Security Index from Economist Impact and Corteva Agriscience considers availability, affordability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation (<https://impact.economist.com/sustainability/project/food-security-index>). However, in this work, we are particularly interested in the impacts of climate tipping points on food security; therefore, we focus on the food security factors most strongly affected by climate, namely food production. We focus on the direct impacts on crop growth, though climate can also affect pests and plant diseases (e.g., Bebbler et al. 2013) and farm labour (e.g., Hertel and de Lima 2020). Livestock would also be similarly affected (e.g., Rojas-Downing et al. 2017), but are excluded from this study.

To assess potential impacts of climate tipping points on agriculture, we consider three main approaches with varying degrees of sophistication and information requirements. Process-based crop modelling is arguably the most holistic approach, with the potential to account for changing farming practices, interactions among factors, and improved interpretability. Still, it also requires the most information on crop properties. Data-based methods, with either statistical or machine learning models, aim to extract patterns and relationships from the data itself. They may be more forgiving of missing a priori information; however, their performance depends heavily on the quality and quantity of the input data. Lastly, there is the indices method, where conditions required for crop growth are defined based on prior knowledge, and potential impacts are assessed through examining changes in these conditions. A highly sophisticated example of this approach is the Global Agro-ecological Zoning (GAEZ) model (FAO and IIASA 2025, <https://data.apps.fao.org/gaez/>). In this milestone, we outline the factors that determine crop growth and identify indices that can quantify them. These can feed directly into index-based assessments, but are also crucial for variable/feature definition in machine-learning-based approaches and can help with understanding process-based models.

2.1.1 Impact perspectives

Climate’s impact on the agricultural sector can be examined from several perspectives. The measure of interest is generally crop yield, though the timescale may differ. On a year-to-year basis, weather conditions

can affect yield by altering crop productivity. To capture this, the variables and indices need to capture how conditions vary from one year to the next. If we focus on the most extreme impacts, such as crop failure, similar variables and indices may be used, though the threshold may differ. Lastly, if changing climate results in significant shifts in environmental conditions, a region previously suitable for a certain crop may become unsuitable altogether, and vice versa. Indices for defining crop suitability would be more focused on shifts in climate conditions rather than on year-to-year variability and have a stronger spatial focus. In this report, indices are noted for their ability to capture impacts on productivity, shock events (crop failure), and/or suitability (Table 1).

2.1.2 Indicators for conditions favourable/harmful to crop growth and yield

Main factors that affect crop yield can generally be grouped into the following: temperature, water, soil, radiation, crop properties, and field management (van Klompenburg et al. 2020). A list of indices capturing these factors is shown in Table 1. Temperature is one of the most common and often the most highly ranked properties affecting yield. It can be measured as average, minimum, and/or maximum temperatures at various stages of crop development. It can also be expressed as the accumulation of heat units and the frequency of threshold exceedance. Water is a similarly important limiting factor for crops. Depending on the temporal perspective, this can be measured by aridity at climate scales, by droughts as extreme events, or by precipitation indices for year-to-year variability. Soil properties include soil type (sandy, clay, etc.), which may be considered a static property at weather and climate timescales; soil nutrient information, which is tied to the locale but can also be influenced by farming practices; and soil quality, which can be affected by farming practices and climate conditions. Crop properties can be generalised across crop species or specific to each cultivar, but are considered fixed per crop or cultivar, without spatial-temporal dimensions. They are related to the thresholds at which conditions are considered favourable for each crop, which are listed separately in Table 2. Lastly, field management includes irrigation, fertilisation, and other farming practices. These are the human factors which require separate consideration and are not included in this report.

Table 1: Indicators for conditions favourable/harmful to crop growth and yield. More than one definition may exist for each indicator.

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
Crop properties			
Cardinal temperatures	Minimum/base, optimal, and maximum cardinal temperatures	The temperature range suitable for the growth of a specific crop	Suitability, productivity
Growing season	Start and end of growing season	According to the present-day crop calendar (e.g. Tang et al. 2024, Van Tricht et al. 2023)	Suitability
		When 5-day weighted mean temperature exceeds minimum cardinal temperature for five consecutive days; except cool season crop (e.g. spring wheat, barley, canola, oat, and rye), which is planted in spring and matures in summer and has season end defined as earlier of 31st August (in Canada) or when the weighted mean daily maximum temperature reaches the maximum cardinal temperature for five consecutive days in August (Qian et al. 2010)	Suitability
		Date of last spring (killing) frost ($T_{min} < 0^{\circ}C$ or $-2^{\circ}C$ for killing frost) and first autumn (killing) frost (Qian et al. 2010)	Suitability
	Growing season length	Time between the start and the end of the growing season	Suitability, productivity
		Number of (killing) frost-free days (Qian et al. 2010)	Suitability, productivity
		Days when daily mean temperature is above $5^{\circ}C$ and soil moisture is sufficient according to a water balance model considering precipitation, soil moisture, and evapotranspiration (GAEZ v5; FAO and IIASA 2025)	Suitability, productivity
Phenological development	Development Stage index (DVS; de Wit et al. 2019)	-0.1 = sowing 0 = emergence 1.0 = flowering 2.0 = maturity Progression through accumulation of heat/degree days	-
	Pre-planting window, planting	Phases separated by the development stages noted above	-

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
	window, vegetative phase, flowering phase, yield formation phase, and harvest window (Paudel et al. 2021)		
Temperature			
Degree days	Growing degree days/heat units	Sum of daily degrees above the defined threshold temperature (e.g. minimum cardinal temperature)	Productivity
	Degree-days in the growing season	Cumulative growing degree days during the growing season only	Productivity
	Effective growing degree days	Growing degree days with an additional day-length factor (Bootsma et al. 2005)	Productivity
	Harmful degree days	Degree-days above upper threshold (e.g. maximum cardinal temperature)	Productivity, shock
	Physiological development day (PDD)	Accumulation in days of conditions favourable for crop development, with conditions constrained by daylight hours and cardinal temperatures (Schoving et al. 2020)	Productivity
Average temperature	Annual average temperature, average temperature during growing season, average maximum/minimum daily temperature		Suitability
Frost	Date of first autumnal frost and last spring frost	A frost day is defined as when the daily minimum temperature reaches below 0°C	Suitability, productivity
	Frost-free period or number of frost-free days	Between the last spring frost and the first autumnal frost, or the total number of frost-free days in a year	Suitability, productivity
	Killing frost	Daily minimum temperature < -2°C	Shock
	Ice-freeze damage during the non-growing season (overwintering crops only)	Number of days with minimum temperature below the critical killing temperature during non-growing season (Parker 1963, Krueger 1983, Embree 1984, Coleman 1992, Qian et al. 2010)	Shock

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
	Frost damage index	Accumulation over time of temperature below damage threshold, similar to growing degree days (Tschurr et al. 2023)	Productivity, shock
Heat wave/cool spell	Frequency (number of events), length (mean/maximum days per event), severity (mean temperature during event)	Consecutive days during the growing season with temperatures above/below the cardinal maximum/minimum temperature are counted as a heat wave/cool spell event	Shock
Water			
Water deficit	Water balance deficit	Average daily potential evapotranspiration minus precipitation, accumulated over the growing period (Bootsma et al. 2005)	Suitability, productivity, shock
	Soil water deficit	Amount of water shortage below 50% of the soil's plant available water holding capacity (AWC) AWC = 100 mm (sandy loam), 150 mm (loam), 200 mm (clay loam), and 250 mm (clay) (Shields and Sly 1984)	Productivity, shock
	Stress degree days	Sum over time, of the difference between canopy and ambient temperature during the warmest time of the day; the plant is water-stressed when canopy temperature > ambient temperature (Jackson et al. 1977)	Productivity, shock
	Crop water stress index	Energy balance-based calculation of water stress using ambient, canopy, wet bulb, and dry bulb temperatures, representing the difference between potential and actual evapotranspiration; water is stressed when actual evapotranspiration falls below potential evapotranspiration (Jackson et al. 1981)	Productivity, shock
Aridity index (Stadler 1998)	Lang's 1920 rain factor index	Ratio between mean annual precipitation and annual mean temperature	Suitability
	Meyer's 1926 precipitation-saturation deficit ratio	Ratio of precipitation to saturation deficit (saturation vapour pressure minus vapour pressure); assumes evaporation is a function of saturation deficit.	Suitability
	Thornthwaite's indices	Precipitation Effectiveness Index (1931): the sum of monthly precipitation to evaporation	Suitability

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
		ratio at a location, estimated using monthly mean values Aridity Index (1948 & subsequent revisions): relates annual moisture deficit to annual potential evapotranspiration	
	UNEP aridity index	Mean annual precipitation divided by mean annual potential evapotranspiration (UNEP 1992)	Suitability
	De Martonne aridity index	$AI = \text{mean annual precipitation [mm]} / (\text{annual mean temperature [}^{\circ}\text{C]} + 10)$ (Baltas 2007)	Suitability
	Monthly De Martonne aridity index	$AI = (12 * \text{monthly mean precip}) / (\text{monthly mean } T + 10)$ (Baltas 2007)	Suitability
	Emberger aridity index	$AI = (100 * \text{average precipitation [mm]}) / (\text{warmest month } T [^{\circ}\text{C}]^2 - \text{coldest month } T [^{\circ}\text{C}]^2)$	Suitability
	Pinna combinative index	$AI = ((\text{mean annual precipitation} / (\text{mean annual temperature} + 10)) + ((12 * \text{mean precipitation of driest month}) / (\text{mean temperature of driest month} + 10))) / 2$ (Baltas 2007)	Suitability
	Temperature-precipitation diagram	Dryness is defined by temperature-dependent precipitation thresholds; the warmer the temperature, the higher the precipitation threshold (Gausson 1956, Baltas 2007)	Suitability
	Budyko's (1951) radiational index of dryness	The number of times the radiation can evaporate the precipitation, calculated as: $\text{mean annual net radiation} / (\text{mean annual precipitation} * \text{latent heat of vaporisation})$ (Budyko 1951)	Suitability
Drought index	Percent of normal precipitation	Percentage ratio of precipitation to climatological average; monthly, seasonal, or annual (Svoboda and Fuchs 2016)	Productivity, shock
	Deciles	Deciles of the climatological record (Svoboda and Fuchs 2016)	Productivity, shock
	Palmer drought severity index	Measure of long-term meteorological drought using a water balance approach; function of temperature, precipitation, and available water capacity of the soil (Palmer 1965, Stadler 1998)	Productivity, shock

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
	Palmer-Z index	Based on the Palmer drought severity index, but for short-term drought	Productivity, shock
	Crop moisture index	Short-term agricultural drought, based on the Palmer drought severity index, which uses weekly precipitation and temperature (Palmer 1968)	Productivity, shock
	Standardised precipitation(-evapo transpiration) index (SPI, SPEI)	Standardised comparison of the precipitation(-evapotranspiration) relative to the climatological mean for the time of year	Productivity, shock
	Quick drought response index	Indicator of short-term drought based on satellite and ground-based measurements (https://quickdri.unl.edu)	Productivity, shock
	Dependable rain	Amount of rain that statistically occurs four in five years (Le Houerou et al. 1993, Stadler 1998)	Suitability
	Root zone soil moisture (RZSM)	Soil moisture in the top 1-2 metres layer of soil; observation- or model-based (Li et al. 2019, Carranza et al. 2021)	Productivity
	Vegetation health index (VHI)	Satellite-derived drought index considering greenness and temperature (e.g. Zeng et al. 2023)	Productivity, shock
	Temporally fixed, spatially varying environmental conditions		
	Soil type: World reference base for soil resources (WRB)	An international soil classification system for present-day soil types (IUSS Working Group WRB 2022)	Suitability
	Soil quality	Soil quality from Global Agro-Ecological Zoning (GAEZ v5; FAO and IIASA 2025, https://data.apps.fao.org/gaez), based on the Harmonized World Soil Database, a global inventory of soil properties (developed by FAO and IIASA, https://www.fao.org/soils-portal/data-hub/soil-maps-and-databases/harmonized-world-soil-database-v20/en/). Soil quality is assessed across eight dimensions: nutrient availability, nutrient retention capacity, rooting conditions, oxygen availability for roots, presence of salinity and	Suitability

Group/indicator	Measure	Definition	Impact type
		sodicity, presence of lime and gypsum, and workability.	
	GAEZ exclusion layer	Based on present-day data, areas excluded from consideration for agricultural usage due to their protected status, biodiversity value, or being wetlands (FAO and IIASA 2025)	Suitability
	Photoperiod	Length of daylight hours in a day; important for certain crops such as soybean, a short-day plant where longer days impede development (Setiyono et al. 2007)	Suitability
Vegetation indices			
	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	Satellite-based measure of vegetation health and greenness using near infrared and red channels	Productivity
	Leaf area index (LAI)	Ratio of total canopy leaf area to the ground area	Productivity
	Fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (FAPAR)	The fraction of incoming solar radiation within the photosynthetically active spectra absorbed. It's a measure of the amount of energy used by the plant and reflects its primary productivity.	Productivity
CO₂ fertilisation			
	CO ₂ concentration	CO ₂ fertilisation refers to the enhancement of plant photosynthesis with elevated atmospheric CO ₂ concentrations. C ₃ crops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ~18% increase in yield with ~200ppm increase in CO₂ concentration, under non-stress conditions • Varies by crop and environmental conditions • Effect is reduced by nitrogen deficiency, wet conditions, and higher temperatures C ₄ crops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not affected except under drought (Ainsworth and Long 2021) 	Productivity

Table 2: Crop-specific properties and thresholds for three major crops.

Property	Wheat	Maize	Soybean
Base/minimum cardinal temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -1°C¹, 2°C² (leaf initiation) • 3°C (shoot growth)¹ • 2°C (root growth)¹ • 3.5°C (sowing to emergence)¹ • -1°C (vernalisation; i.e. cold period before flowering)¹ • 1.5°C (terminal spikelet)¹ • 9.5°C (anthesis)¹ • 9°C (grain filling)¹ • 5°C^{3,9,10} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10°C^{3,10} • 20°C (seed germination)⁵ • 7°C (leaf initiation)⁶ • 11°C (shoot growth)⁶ • 13°C (root growth)⁶ • 10°C (sowing to emergence)⁶ • 9°C (sowing to tassel initiation)⁶ • 8°C (anthesis)⁶ • 8°C (grain filling)⁶ • 6°C (whole plant)⁶ • 10°C (germination)⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10°C^{3,10} • 2°C⁷ • 10°C (growth), 15°C (crop production)⁹
Optimal cardinal temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 22°C (leaf initiation)^{1,2} • 20°C (shoot growth)¹ • <16°C (root growth)¹ • 22°C (sowing to emergence)¹ • 5°C (vernalisation)¹ • 11°C (terminal spikelet)¹ • 21°C (anthesis)¹ • 21°C (grain filling)¹ • 25°C³ • 16-25°C (germination, tillering, and leaf development) then lower to 14°C during reproductive phase (grain filling, maturity)⁸ • 15 to 20°C⁹ • 18°C or more (ripening period)⁹ • 15 to 23°C¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30°C³ • 33°C (seed germination)⁵ • 31°C (leaf initiation)⁶ • 31°C (shoot growth)⁶ • 26°C (root growth)⁶ • 29°C (sowing to emergence)⁶ • 28°C (sowing to tassel initiation)⁶ • 30.5°C (anthesis)⁶ • 26°C (grain filling)⁶ • 31°C (whole plant)⁶ • 18 to 20°C (germination)⁹ • 18 to 33°C¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30°C^{3,7} • 18 to 35°C⁹ • 20 to 33°C¹⁰
Maximum cardinal temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24°C (leaf initiation)¹ • >21°C (shoot growth)¹ • >25°C (root growth)¹ • 33°C (sowing to emergence)¹ • 16°C (vernalisation)¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 35°C³ • 45°C (seed germination)⁵ • 41°C (leaf initiation)⁶ • 39°C (shoot growth)⁶ • 40°C (root growth)⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 35°C³ • 40°C⁷ • 38°C¹⁰

Property	Wheat	Maize	Soybean
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >20°C (terminal spikelet)¹ • 31°C (anthesis)¹ • 35°C (grain filling)¹ • 30°C (spring wheat), 35°C (winter wheat)³ • 27°C¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40°C (sowing to emergence)⁶ • 39°C (sowing to tassel initiation)⁶ • 37°C (anthesis)⁶ • 36°C (grain filling)⁶ • 42°C (whole plant)⁶ • 45°C⁹ • 47°C¹⁰ 	
Lethal minimum temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -17.2 ± 1.2°C¹ • -9°C with 3 day lag (winter wheat)⁴ • Winter wheat: tolerant of winter frost to -20°C in early stages (requires vernalisation) but not to spring frost during growth periods⁹ • 0°C during early growth and -20°C otherwise¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -2°C⁶ • Easily killed by frost^{9,10} 	
Lethal maximum temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 47.5 ± 0.5°C¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 46°C⁶ 	
Degree days		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2500 to 3000 degree days (medium varieties), 1800 degree days (early varieties), 3700 or more degree days (late varieties)⁹ 	
Photoperiod	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neutral day (12-14 hours) or long day (>14 hours)¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Day-neutral or short-day⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Germination: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Critical daylength for zero development: 18-20 hours⁷ ◦ Optimal daylength: 12-13 hours⁷ • Short-day plant⁹ (<12 hours)¹⁰ but requirements vary with variety and temperature⁹
Physiological development days			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To maturity: 31-46 physiological development days⁷

Property	Wheat	Maize	Soybean
Water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptable; ideal conditions: 25-150cm annual rainfall distributed evenly throughout the season; excess during the early season can lead to root disease, drought during the late season can affect yield⁸ • Most sensitive to water deficit during flowering, followed by yield formation period; also requires good pre- and early-season rainfall for establishment, but not during ripening stage⁹ • Annual rainfall: 750-900mm (optimal), 300-1600mm (absolute)¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water deficit can strongly affect yield, particularly deficit during flowering and also yield formation periods, less so during vegetative (early) and ripening (final) periods⁹ • Annual rainfall: 600-1200mm (optimal), 400-1800mm (absolute)¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive to water deficit particularly during later flowering and early yield formation periods; optimal water also required during germination; less sensitive during vegetative period and near maturity⁹ • Annual rainfall: 600-1500mm (optimal), 450-1800mm (absolute)¹⁰
Soil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptable; loamy or clay loam soils are ideal; soil fertility is key to high yield⁸ • Medium textures are preferred; peaty soils to be avoided; optimum pH: 6 to 8; moderate sensitivity to soil salinity⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does well in most soils, though less so in extremes (dense clay and very sandy soil)⁹ • Sensitive to waterlogging; high soil fertility demands for high producing varieties; moderate sensitivity to soil salinity⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All soils except very sandy⁹ • Sensitive to waterlogging but not too much to soil salinity; optimum soil pH: 6 to 6.5⁹
Growth cycle length	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 to 130 days (spring wheat), 180 to 250 days (winter wheat)⁹ • 90 to 250 days¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Above 20°C: 80 to 110 days (early grain varieties) or 110 to 140 days (medium varieties); 10 to 20 days longer for each 0.5°C decrease in mean daily temperature⁹ • 65-365 days¹⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 to 130 days or more⁹ • 75 to 180 days¹⁰

References: ¹Porter and Gawith (1999; review), ²White et al. (2012; USA), ³Qian et al. (2010; Canada), ⁴Tschurr et al. (2023), ⁵Amin et al. (2024; lab-based), ⁶Sánchez et al. (2014; review), ⁷Schoving et al. (2020; Europe), ⁸Optimal Conditions for Wheat Cultivation - Agriculture Notes by Agriculture.Institute (2023), ⁹Crop Information | Land & Water | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, ¹⁰FAO GAEZv4 - ECOCROP

2.2. Water security

Similar to food security, water security is affected by many factors beyond supply and demand. For instance, the Water Security Index by Babel et al. (2020) includes information about water quality, governance, infrastructure, cost, and disaster preparedness. However, again, similar to food security, we focus on indices and measures of water security that address the hydrological aspects of water supply that can be most impacted by climate tipping, as well as simple metrics for estimating water demand.

A standard measure of water scarcity is the water resources available per capita (i.e. the water crowding/Falkenmark Index), with a threshold of 1000 m³ per capita per year defined as water-scarce (Gosling and Arnell 2016, McNally et al. 2019). The demand is a simple function of population size, while the water supply is often represented by the mean annual river runoff. Alternatively, the ratio of water withdrawals to available water is another standard measure that accounts more sophisticatedly for water demand; a ratio of 0.4 is considered water scarce. Other measures of water scarcity include those for specific uses, such as soil moisture deficit and water scarcity for agriculture, as discussed above under food security, as well as modified versions of simple indices with additional consideration for a country's adaptive capacity and environmental water needs. A list of indices and studies for water security is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Water security indices.

Index/measure	Description	Usage context and details
Water Security Index	<p>5 dimensions - water supply and sanitation, water productivity, water-related disasters, water environment, water governance</p> <p>12 indicators - water availability, quality of water supplied, disaster preparedness, economic value of water, effect of polluting factors, potential to adapt to future changes, etc.</p> <p>A set of potential variables to quantify each indicator - per-capita water use, population access to piped water supply, pH of supplied water, waterborne disease factor, water price, flood risk mapping, adaptability factor, etc.</p> <p>The variables are normalised and aggregated to give a score for each dimension.</p>	The framework was developed for city-scale analysis and used to assess water security in Bangkok. (Babel et al. 2020)
Global water security index	<p>Four security criteria: availability, accessibility to services, safety and quality, and management</p> <p>Each criterion is measured by a set of indicators, aggregated with different weights: water scarcity index, drought index, groundwater depletion, access to sanitation, access to drinking water, water quality index, global flood frequency, world governance index, transboundary legal framework, transboundary political tension</p>	Global grid-scale assessment (Gain et al. 2016)
Water Crowding Index (WCI)/Falkenmark categories	<p>Annual water resources in a watershed per capita, or inversely, the number of people per unit of water resource (Falkenmark 1989)</p> <p>m³ per capita per year: No stress: >1700 Water stress: 1700–1000 Water scarcity: 1000–500 Absolute water scarcity: <500</p>	<p>Global, country-scale assessments for future climate scenarios</p> <p>Supply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global hydrological models driven by input from global climate models • Runoff redistributed across the river basin according to the

Index/measure	Description	Usage context and details
		spatial distribution of discharge (Schewe et al. 2014) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average annual runoff per grid cell from hydrological model (Gosling and Arnell 2016) Demand: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on population from SSP projections
Social water stress index (SWSI)	Modifies the Falkenmark water crowding index with the Human Development Index (HDI), which uses life expectancy, educational attainment, and GDP per capita as proxies to additionally consider societal adaptive capacity (Ohlsson 2000, Damkjaer and Taylor 2017)	Global, country-scale assessments and comparisons with traditional/Falkenmark WCI to identify countries with adaptive capacity to reduce the potential impact of freshwater flux shortages
Water Stress Index (WSI)	Ratio of water withdrawals to resources. Captures water stress from climate and from pressures population and water withdrawals $WSI = \text{water withdrawals} / \text{water available}$ $WSI > 0.4$: exposure to water scarcity (Rockström et al. 2009)	Country and regional assessments for future climate scenarios Supply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global hydrological models driven by input from global climate models Average annual runoff per grid cell from hydrological model (Gosling and Arnell 2016) Demand (withdrawals): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rescaled to SSP population projections from SRES-based water withdrawal projections from Shen et al. (2014) (Gosling and Arnell 2016) Modelled using water use model, considering irrigation, livestock, households, thermal power plants, and manufacturing industry (Smakhtin et al. 2004)

Index/measure	Description	Usage context and details
WSI _{EWR}	<p>Water stress index with additional consideration of environmental water requirements (EWRs, river flow required for ecosystem maintenance)</p> <p>$WSI_{EWR} = \text{withdrawals} / (\text{mean annual runoff} - \text{EWR})$</p> <p>(Smakhtin et al. 2004, Damkjaer and Taylor 2017)</p>	<p>EWR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimated using combinations of data analysis, modelling, and expert judgement (Acreman and Dunbar 2004) • Basin-specific • Depends on conservation status and management objective (Smakhtin et al. 2004)
Water stress anomaly	Anomaly of (monthly) streamflow from climatological mean for that month	Catchment scale acute water scarcity monitoring in Africa (McNally et al. 2019)

3. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objective (SO) of TipESM.

SO7	<p>To provide a new understanding of the climate, societal and ecosystem consequences of crossing climate thresholds and TPs. KPIs: A report on the impact of climate tipping events on natural and human systems, encompassing the vulnerability and exposure of these systems. (Deliverables: D7.1, D7.2, D7.3 Milestones: MS5, MS8).</p> <p>Contribution of this milestone: In this milestone report, we focus on two sectors that may be affected by climate tipping points: food and water. In particular, we are interested in changes in food and water security that may directly result from crossing climate thresholds. Factors that can affect agricultural productivity and suitability are identified, along with indices that quantify water scarcity. These will feed into subsequent project work assessing changes in food and water security in tipping simulations.</p>	WPs: 1,7, and 8
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4. References

Acreman, M.C., Dunbar, M.J., 2004. Defining environmental river flow requirements – a review. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 8, 861–876. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-8-861-2004>

Ainsworth, E.A., Long, S.P., 2021. 30 years of free-air carbon dioxide enrichment (FACE): What have we learned about future crop productivity and its potential for adaptation? *Global Change Biology* 27, 27–49. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15375>

Amin, F., Shah, F., Ullah, S., Shah, W., Ahmed, I., Ali, B., Khan, A.A., Malik, T., Mustafa, A.E.-Z.M.A., 2024. The germination response of *Zea mays* L. to osmotic potentials across optimal temperatures via halo-thermal time model. *Sci Rep* 14, 3225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-53129-6>

Babel, M.S., Shinde, V.R., Sharma, D., Dang, N.M., 2020. Measuring water security: A vital step for climate change adaptation. *Environmental Research* 185, 109400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109400>

Baltas, E., 2007. Spatial distribution of climatic indices in northern Greece. *Meteorological Applications* 14, 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.7>

Bebber, D.P., Ramotowski, M.A.T., Gurr, S.J., 2013. Crop pests and pathogens move polewards in a warming world. *Nature Clim Change* 3, 985–988. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1990>

Bootsma, A., Gameda, S., McKenney, D. W., 2005. Impacts of potential climate change on selected agroclimatic indices in Atlantic Canada. *Can. J. Soil. Sci.* 85, 329–343. <https://doi.org/10.4141/S04-019>

Budyko, M. I., 1951. O. Klimaticheskikh Factorakh Stoka (On climatic factors and runoff), *Problemyfiz Geog.*, 16, 41-48.

Carranza, C., Nolet, C., Pezij, M., van der Ploeg, M., 2021. Root zone soil moisture estimation with Random Forest. *Journal of Hydrology* 593, 125840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2020.125840>

Coleman, W.K., 1992. A proposed winter-injury classification for apple trees on the northern fringe of commercial production. *Can. J. Plant Sci.* 72, 507–516. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjps92-064>

Crop Information | Land & Water | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. URL <https://www.fao.org/land-water/databases-and-software/crop-information/en/> (accessed 25 Nov 2025).

Damkjaer, S., Taylor, R., 2017. The measurement of water scarcity: Defining a meaningful indicator. *Ambio* 46, 513–531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-017-0912-z>

de Wit, A., Boogaard, H., Fumagalli, D., Janssen, S., Knapen, R., van Kraalingen, D., Supit, I., van der Wijngaart, R., van Diepen, K., 2019. 25 years of the WOFOST cropping systems model. *Agricultural Systems* 168, 154–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2018.06.018>

Embree, C., 1984. An assessment and illustration of winter injury to selected apple cultivars in nova-scotia, 1980-81. *Fruit Varieties Journal* 38, 8–13.

Falkenmark, M., 1989. The Massive Water Scarcity Now Threatening Africa: Why Isn't It Being Addressed? *Ambio* 18, 112–118.

FAO and IIASA, 2025. Global Agro-ecological Zoning version 5 (GAEZ v5) Model Documentation. <https://github.com/un-fao/gaezv5/wiki>

FAO GAEZv4 - ECOCROP. URL <https://gaez.fao.org/pages/ecocrop-find-plant> (accessed 25 Nov 2025)

Gain, A.K., Giupponi, C., Wada, Y., 2016. Measuring global water security towards sustainable development goals. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11, 124015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/12/124015>

Gaussen, H., 1956. Le XVIIIe congrès international de géographie, Rio de Janeiro, août 1956. *Annales De Géographie* 353: 1–19.

Gosling, S.N., Arnell, N.W., 2016. A global assessment of the impact of climate change on water scarcity. *Climatic Change* 134, 371–385. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0853-x>

Hertel, T.W., de Lima, C.Z., 2020. Viewpoint: Climate impacts on agriculture: Searching for keys under the streetlight. *Food Policy* 95, 101954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101954>

IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification

system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

Jackson, R.D., Reginato, R.J., Idso, S.B., 1977. Wheat canopy temperature: A practical tool for evaluating water requirements. *Water Resources Research* 13, 651–656. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR013i003p00651>

Jackson, R.D., Idso, S.B., Reginato, R.J., Pinter Jr., P.J., 1981. Canopy temperature as a crop water stress indicator. *Water Resources Research* 17, 1133–1138. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR017i004p01133>

Krueger, R.R., 1983. The Orchard Industry's Response to Low-Temperature Injury in the Okanagan Valley. *Canadian Geographies / Géographies canadiennes* 27, 313–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0064.1983.tb00840.x>

Le Houerou, H.N., Popov, G.F., and See, L., 1993. Agro-bioclimatic Classification of Africa, Agrometeorology Series Working Paper No. 6. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organisation.

Li, B., Rodell, M., Kumar, S., Beaudoin, H.K., Getirana, A., Zaitchik, B.F., de Goncalves, L.G., Cossetin, C., Bhanja, S., Mukherjee, A., Tian, S., Tangdamrongsub, N., Long, D., Nanteza, J., Lee, J., Policelli, F., Goni, I.B., Daira, D., Bila, M., de Lannoy, G., Mocko, D., Steele-Dunne, S.C., Save, H., Bettadpur, S., 2019. Global GRACE Data Assimilation for Groundwater and Drought Monitoring: Advances and Challenges. *Water Resources Research* 55, 7564–7586. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018WR024618>

McNally, A., Verdin, K., Harrison, L., Getirana, A., Jacob, J., Shukla, S., Arsenault, K., Peters-Lidard, C., Verdin, J.P., 2019. Acute Water-Scarcity Monitoring for Africa. *Water* 11, 1968. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11101968>

Ohlsson, L., 2000. Water conflicts and social resource scarcity. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Part B: Hydrology, Oceans and Atmosphere* 25, 213–220. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-1909\(00\)00006-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-1909(00)00006-X)

Optimal Conditions for Wheat Cultivation - Agriculture Notes by Agriculture.Institute, 2023. URL <https://agriculture.institute/agriculture-fundamentals/optimal-conditions-wheat-cultivation/> (accessed 13 Nov 2025).

Palmer, W. C., 1965. Meteorological drought. *US. Weather Bureau Res. Paper*, 45, 1-58.

Palmer, W. C., 1968. Keeping track of crop moisture conditions, nationwide: the Crop Moisture Index. *Weatherwise*, 21:156–161.

Parker, J., 1963. Cold resistance in woody plants. *Bot. Rev* 29, 123–201.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02860820>

Paudel, D., Boogaard, H., de Wit, A., Janssen, S., Osinga, S., Pylaniadis, C., Athanasiadis, I.N., 2021. Machine learning for large-scale crop yield forecasting. *Agricultural Systems* 187, 103016.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2020.103016>

Porter, J.R., Gawith, M., 1999. Temperatures and the growth and development of wheat: a review. *European Journal of Agronomy* 10, 23–36. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301\(98\)00047-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(98)00047-1)

Qian, B., Zhang, X., Chen, K., Feng, Y., O'Brien, T., 2010. Observed Long-Term Trends for Agroclimatic Conditions in Canada. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology* 49.
<https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JAMC2275.1>

Rockström, J., Falkenmark, M., Karlberg, L., Hoff, H., Rost, S., Gerten, D., 2009. Future water availability for global food production: The potential of green water for increasing resilience to global change. *Water Resources Research* 45, 2007WR006767. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007WR006767>

Rojas-Downing, M.M., Nejadhashemi, A.P., Harrigan, T., Woznicki, S.A., 2017. Climate change and livestock: Impacts, adaptation, and mitigation. *Climate Risk Management* 16, 145–163.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2017.02.001>

Sánchez, B., Rasmussen, A., Porter, J.R., 2014. Temperatures and the growth and development of maize and rice: a review. *Global Change Biology* 20, 408–417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12389>

Schewe, J., Heinke, J., Gerten, D., Haddeland, I., Arnell, N.W., Clark, D.B., Dankers, R., Eisner, S., Fekete, B.M., Colón-González, F.J., Gosling, S.N., Kim, H., Liu, X., Masaki, Y., Portmann, F.T., Satoh, Y., Stacke, T., Tang, Q., Wada, Y., Wisser, D., Albrecht, T., Frieler, K., Piontek, F., Warszawski, L., Kabat, P., 2014. Multimodel assessment of water scarcity under climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 111, 3245–3250. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1222460110>

Schoving, C., Stöckle, C.O., Colombet, C., Champolivier, L., Debaeke, P., Maury, P., 2020. Combining Simple Phenotyping and Photothermal Algorithm for the Prediction of Soybean Phenology: Application to a Range of Common Cultivars Grown in Europe. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.01755>

Setiyono, T.D., Weiss, A., Specht, J., Bastidas, A.M., Cassman, K.G., Dobermann, A., 2007. Understanding and modelling the effect of temperature and day length on soybean phenology under high-yield conditions. *Field Crops Research* 100, 257–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2006.07.011>

Shen, Y., Oki, T., Kanae, S., Hanasaki, N., Utsumi, N., Kiguchi, M., 2014. Projection of future world water resources under SRES scenarios: an integrated assessment. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 59, 1775–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2013.862338>

Shields, J.A., Sly, W.K., 1984. Aridity indices derived from soil and climatic parameters. Research Branch, Agriculture Canada, Ottawa.

Smakhtin, V., Revenga, C., Döll, P., 2004. A Pilot Global Assessment of Environmental Water Requirements and Scarcity. *Water International* 29, 307–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060408691785>

Stadler, S.J., 1998. Aridity indices, in: *Encyclopedia of Hydrology and Lakes, Encyclopedia of Earth Science*. Springer Netherlands, pp. 78–83. https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-4497-6_20

Svoboda, M.D., Fuchs, B.A., 2016. *Handbook of drought indicators and indices*. World Meteorological Organisation, Geneva.

Tang, F.H.M., Nguyen, T.H., Conchedda, G., Casse, L., Tubiello, F.N., Maggi, F., 2024. CROPGRIDS: a global geo-referenced dataset of 173 crops. *Sci Data* 11, 413. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03247-7>

Tschurr, F., Kirchgessner, N., Hund, A., Kronenberg, L., Anderegg, J., Walter, A., Roth, L., 2023. Frost Damage Index: The Antipode of Growing Degree Days. *Plant Phenomics* 5, 0104. <https://doi.org/10.34133/plantphenomics.0104>

United Nations Environment Programme, 1992. *World Atlas of Desertification*.

van Klompenburg, T., Kassahun, A., Catal, C., 2020. Crop yield prediction using machine learning: A systematic literature review. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 177, 105709.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2020.105709>

Van Tricht, K., Degerickx, J., Gilliams, S., Zanaga, D., Battude, M., Grosu, A., Brombacher, J., Lesiv, M., Bayas, J.C.L., Karanam, S., Fritz, S., Becker-Reshef, I., Franch, B., Mollà-Bononad, B., Boogaard, H., Pratihast, A.K., Koetz, B., Szantoi, Z., 2023. WorldCereal: a dynamic open-source system for global-scale, seasonal, and reproducible crop and irrigation mapping. *Earth System Science Data* 15, 5491–5515.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-5491-2023>

White, J.W., Kimball, B.A., Wall, G.W., Ottman, M.J., 2012. Cardinal temperatures for wheat leaf appearance as assessed from varied sowing dates and infrared warming. *Field Crops Research* 137, 213–220.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2012.08.013>

Zeng, J., Zhou, T., Qu, Y., Bento, V.A., Qi, J., Xu, Y., Li, Y., Wang, Q., 2023. An improved global vegetation health index dataset in detecting vegetation drought. *Sci Data* 10, 338.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02255-3>